

QA4EO WP 2220 SI-traceable system development

1 Introduction and summary

This work package focussed on the development of procedures to retrieve traceable total column ozone from solar UV spectra using spectroradiometers. The standard instruments used world-wide for this purpose are Dobson and Brewer spectroradiometers that are operated in their particular networks, and are traceable to well defined reference instruments. Even though these two networks show an excellent homogeneity among their members, there remain unresolved differences among these two instrument types that need to be resolved in order to produce consistent measurements among these two networks, and in view of serving as vicarious references for satellite based retrievals of total column ozone (Gröbner et al., 2021).

PMOD/WRC has developed an independent approach based on a fully characterised spectroradiometer (QASUME) with solar UV irradiance measurements traceable to the SI (Egli et al., in review 2021). A well defined retrieval procedure has been developed and validated that can retrieve total column ozone from these measurements with a full uncertainty budget, which is independent of the Brewer and Dobson reference instruments. Therefore, this system can serve as an independent reference for total column ozone measurements. The QASUME spectroradiometer was operated during the ATMOZ campaign at Izana in 2016, the RBCC-E campaigns in Huelva in 2017, 2019, and 2021 and at PMOD/WRC during successive periods alongside 4 Brewer and 3 Dobson spectroradiometers.

The KOHERENT system is based on a commercial diode-array spectroradiometer system. Its advantages are its small size, robust construction and excellent optical characteristics with very low stray-light in the short UV range. The system has also been at RBCC-E Huelva campaigns and otherwise permanently deployed at PMOD/WRC. The long-term objective is to develop a state-of-the-art low-cost and user-friendly instrument for unattended operation in a total column ozone monitoring network.

2 D.2.2.2-1,2: Comparison of solar UV and TOC measured by Brewer #163, KOHERENT and QASUME at PMOD/WRC

PMOD/WRC is operating the World Calibration Center for UV (WCC-UV) on behalf of the WMO. Several CMC (Calibration and Measurement Capabilities) are listed in the Key Comparison Database of the Bureau International des Poids et Mesures, demonstrating that PMOD/WRC can provide traceable measurements of solar UV irradiance with well established uncertainties. Furthermore, PMOD/WRC can provide calibrations that are traceable to the SI for broadband filter radiometers measuring solar UV irradiance and spectroradiometers measuring spectral solar UV irradiance.

A solar UV intercomparison took place at PMOD/WRC in August 2020 between the reference spectroradiometer QASUME and Brewer #163 and QASUME-II. The report of the comparison is available on the QASUME web-site at:

https://www.pmodwrc.ch/wcc_uv/qasume_audit/reports/2020_08_switzerland_davos.pdf

The results show that all three instruments measure spectral solar UV irradiance within their stated uncertainties, with an agreement better than 5% over the wavelength range 300 nm to 500 nm (363 nm for Br#163).

The total column ozone retrieved by QASUME, Brewer#163 and KOHERENT was compared to Brewer #156, which is part of the Brewer Triad from Meteo Swiss in continuous operation at PMOD/WRC. Additional instruments measuring total column ozone at PMOD/WRC are Brewer B040, B072, Dobson D51, D62, and D101, and a Pandora P120 operating in the Pandonia network.

The comparison between all instruments was performed for the time period from 1 January 2016 to 31 December 2021, or as long as the instruments were operating. The following figures show the comparison between each instrument and Brewer B156, which was chosen as common reference for this comparison.

Figure 1 Relative differences between total column ozone measurements from Brewer #163 to Brewer #156. The measurements shown as blue points were selected when they were within a 5 minute coincident window. The black line is a seasonal (sine) fit to the data with the amplitude as shown in the figure.

Figure 2 Relative differences between total column ozone measurements from QASUME to Brewer #156. The measurements shown as blue points were selected when they were within a 5 minute coincident window. The black line is a seasonal (sine) fit to the data with the amplitude as shown in the figure.

Figure 3 Relative differences between total column ozone measurements from KOHERENT using a double-ratio algorithm to Brewer #156. The measurements shown as blue points were selected when they were within a 5 minute coincident window. The black line is a seasonal (sine) fit to the data with the amplitude as shown in the figure.

The other instruments were compared in a similar way, with their results summarised in Table 1. Of particular interest is Pandora P120, whose total column ozone product is obtained from the Pandonia database, and represents the operational product of the network. The comparison is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Relative differences between total column ozone measurements from PANDORA P120 to Brewer #156. The measurements shown as blue points were selected when they were within a 5 minute coincident window. The black line is a seasonal (sine) fit to the data with the amplitude as shown in the figure.

Table 1 Summary of the comparison of total column ozone of each instrument to Brewer #156, which was selected as local reference.

Instrument	Relative difference in %	Standard deviation in %	Amplitude of seasonal fit in %	Number of data points
B040	-0.35	0.79	0.093	44594
B072	0.16	1.17	0.478	41926
B163	0.40	0.75	0.045	16007
D051	1.21	0.76	0.542	22273
D062	0.92	1.13	0.777	40982
D101	0.15	0.79	0.153	32951
QASUME	1.21	0.95	0.125	1941

Pandora P120	0.09	2.41	2.82	14865
KOHERENT (DR)	0.05	1.06	0.089	11315

The results of Brewer and Dobson are obtained using the IUP ozone absorption cross-sections and applying an effective ozone temperature correction as described in Gröbner et al., 2021.. As shown in Gröbner et al., 2021, the consistency between Brewer and Dobson spectroradiometers can be considerably improved when the temperature dependent ozone absorption cross-sections of Serdyuchenko et al., 2014 (Serdyuchenko, A., Gorshchev, V., Weber, M., Chehade, W., and Burrows, J. P.: High spectral resolution ozone absorption crosssections – Part 2: Temperature dependence, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 7, 625–636, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-7-625-2014>, 2014.) are used, along with the actual effective ozone temperature.

3 D.2.2.2.3: Datasets of TOC and solar UV spectra measured with Brewer #163, QASUME and KOHERENT

The datasets of total column ozone of Brewer #163, QASUME, KOHERENT and Pandora P120 are stored as matlab format files and available on request. They can also be exported to a more common format on request.

4 Report and datasets of Cal/Val field campaigns

No specific Cal/Val field campaigns within this WP took place during phase1.

5 Publications acknowledging QA4EO financial support

Gröbner, J., Schill, H., Egli, L., and Stübi, R.: Consistency of total column ozone measurements between the Brewer and Dobson spectroradiometers of the LKO Arosa and PMOD/WRC Davos, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 14, 3319–3331, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-14-3319-2021>, 2021.

Zuber, R., Köhler, U., Egli, L., Ribnitzky, M., Steinbrecht, W., and Gröbner, J.: Total ozone column intercomparison of Brewers, Dobsons, and BTS-Solar at Hohenpeißenberg and Davos in 2019/2020, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 14, 4915–4928, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-14-4915-2021>, 2021.

Egli, L., Gröbner, J., Hülsen, G., Schill, H., and Stübi, R.: Traceable total ozone column retrievals from direct solar spectral irradiance measurements in the ultraviolet, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 15, 1917–1930, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-15-1917-2022>, 2022.

Kouremeti, N., J. Gröbner, and S. Nevas, Stray-light correction methodology for the Precision Solar Spectroradiometer, *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* 2149 012002, 2022. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/2149/1/012002/pdf>.